

Collaboration with the society in scientific projects.

Short overview.

Zofia Bienkowska

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Introduction

In recent years, we can observe a growing interest among scientists, scientific institutions and funding bodies in promoting and communicating scientific research and its findings to the public. One of the manifestations of this trend is EU valorisation policy, which emphasizes the need for dissemination and promotion of the scientific knowledge among citizens. It also promotes more in-depth forms of cooperation such as participation of civil society organizations and communities in turning research results into innovative solutions. The approach of the EU highlights not only the economic value, but also the societal value of science (European Commission, n.d.).

With a growing interest in cooperation with the society there is also a growing number of mechanisms and techniques that allow scientists to reach the society. The need of public involvement in the science-creation and dissemination is corresponding with broader trends in public planning (e.g. transport planning, environmental planning etc.), management and governance that aim to reach maximum levels of democratization (Arnstein 1969; Bickerstaff and Walker 2001; Carr and Halvorsen 2001). However, the field of science-society collaboration is not yet well established (Rowe and Fewer 2005; Warwas et al 2021).

The objective of this report is to provide a concise summary of the existing knowledge regarding science-society collaboration. Due to its limited scope, the report is unable to cover all the available literature on the subject. However, every effort has been made to ensure its comprehensiveness. I searched the key words using Scopus, Google Scholar, Science Direct and Web of Science databases and followed the threads I found, and the authors referenced. The report begins by reviewing existing types of science-society cooperation, with examples provided. It then goes on to identify the challenges and obstacles, as well as the key conditions for success in such collaborations. After this, I summarize the most important aspects regarding evaluation of such collaborations. Finally, I provide practical insights on science-society collaboration from the research project “Embodying Climate Change. Transdisciplinary Research on Urban Overheating” (EmCliC) conducted in 2020 – 2024 (grant no 2019/35/J/HS6/03992). This report is an effect of *EmCliC+ Societal Engagement* research activity, a follow up to the EmCliC project.

The typology of science-society cooperation

For the purpose of this report, the term “cooperation” refers to two-dimensional interactions between actors from different backgrounds. The objective of such cooperation is the exchange of knowledge, as well as the undertaking of joint activities with the aim of creating shared outcomes. It is imperative that the participants in such cooperative endeavour treat one another with respect and equality. When I refer to “science” or “scientists”, I am referring to people and institutions professionally

connected to knowledge creation, employed by universities and research institutions, or funded by scientific grants. The term “society” is used here in the broadest sense to refer to “lay people” who are not professionally involved in science. This category may include citizens, representatives of public institutions, city officials, policy makers, artists, non-governmental organisations, not-institutionalized social initiatives, various stakeholders including business and industry. Importantly, this list is not exhaustive, and its main purpose is to highlight the diversity of actors belonging to the "society" category. It is important to note, however, that the category of "society" also includes scientists. Consequently, in certain instances, scientific expertise does not preclude an individual from being regarded as a constituent of society within the context of collaborative endeavours.

As outlined in the relevant literature, the processes and activities that are in place to include society in scientific research can be described under a variety of terms. The objective here is to demonstrate the range of concepts without selecting one particular option. Rather, the focus is on providing an overview of the available definitions. The further selection of a particular concept in practice may be informed by the specific conditions under which it will be implemented. The following terms were identified during the literature review: “participation”, “cooperation”, “collaboration”, “community development”, “community-based”, “public engagement”, “public involvement”, “inclusive research” and “social valorization”. Although these are not synonyms, what those terms have in common is that **science should not be detached from society and that it is a common good that should be shared and also co-created.**

“The concept of public participation is not well formulated, such that some researchers might disagree with the scope of activities implicitly or explicitly included within the concept by others, and synonyms of uncertain equivalence (e.g. public involvement and public engagement) may be used in place of that term.” (Rowe and Fewer 2005, p.252-253)

The primary objective of this report is to provide a comprehensive overview of the available methods of collaboration between scientists and citizens. To this end, I have included all the aforementioned terms in this report, even though they may, on closer inspection, originate from different theoretical frameworks. For instance, Melanie Nind defines **inclusive research** as a broad and inherently diverse concept that encompasses various approaches, all of which share a focus on making the research process more democratic and participatory (Nind, 2014). These approaches to collaboration are focused on challenging conventional hierarchies of power in research and doing things in solidarity with ordinary people, especially those oppressed or victimized (Nind et al., 2017), rather than studying them from the position of power. Moreover “the focus is on researching in ways that are respectful and inclusive of the community being researched, on problems they feel ownership of, in ways that support them and that involve collaboration and openness” (Nind and Vinha 2013, p. 6). The **participatory research** emphasizes the engagement of research participants in decision-making and research itself, encompassing activities such as research planning, gathering and analysing data,

as well as disseminating and applying the findings (Bourke, 2009). At the same time, the most important component of **community-based approaches**, according to Deborah S. Carr and Kathleen Halvorsen, is their ability to include citizens' local knowledge, understanding local conditions and possibility to practice direct democracy (Carr and Halvorsen 2001). However, these terms are not ultimately distinguished, and they are often used interchangeably (see Rowe and Fewer 2005; Warwas et al 2021).

The inclusive research is distinctive from other forms of research in that it is concerned with doing research **WITH** and **BY** the researched group rather than **ON** them.

(see: Nind and Vinha 2013, Vaughn and Jacques 2020, Reason and Torbet 2001)

In the article mentioned earlier, "A Typology of Public Engagement Mechanisms", Gene Rowe and Lynn J. Frewer (2005) define **participation** as "the practice of involving members of the public in the agenda-setting, decision-making, and policy-forming activities of organizations/ institutions responsible for policy development." (p. 253). However, they notice later that the level of engagement and commitment of the public may vary.

"In some cases, the public may "participate" by being the **passive recipients** of information from the regulators or governing bodies concerned; in other cases, **public input may be sought**, as in the solicitation of public opinion through questionnaires; and in still other cases, there may be **active participation** of public representatives in the decision-making process itself, such as through lay representation on an advisory committee." (Rowe and Fewer 2005, p. 253).

Following that observation, they propose a typology of public participation based on three types of interaction between "sponsors" and "public representatives": communication, consultation and participation (see Figure 1). Under the category "sponsor" authors mean governmental or policy-setting organizations and generally the organizers, so we can also apply this term to project contractors, including the scientists (see: Rowe and Frewer 2005, pp. 254-255).

- **Public Communication**

Information flow is one-way: there is no involvement of the public per se in the sense that public feedback is not required or specifically sought. When the public attempts to provide information, there are no mechanisms specified a priori to deal with this at any level beyond, perhaps, simply recording the information.

- **Public Consultation**

Information is conveyed from members of the public to the sponsors of the initiative, following a process initiated by the sponsor. Significantly, no formal dialogue exists between individual members of the public and the sponsors. The information elicited from the public is believed to represent currently held opinions on the topic in question.

- **Public Participation**

Information is exchanged between members of the public and the sponsors. That is, there is some degree of dialogue in the process that takes place (usually in a group setting), which may involve representatives of both parties in different proportions (depending on the mechanism concerned) or, indeed, only representatives of the public who receive additional information from the sponsors prior to responding. Rather than simple, raw opinions being conveyed to the sponsors, the act of dialogue and negotiation serves to transform opinions in the members of both parties (sponsors and public participants).

Figure 1 The three types of public engagement by Rowe and Frewer (2005, p. 255)

A different way to approach the typology of science-society collaboration is the stage of the project when the collaboration activities are implemented.

Figure 1 Stages of cooperation application. Own design.

Activities undertaken prior to the research itself may include participatory research design – the type of research that includes the research group in the process from the

very beginning (see more: Bagnoli and Clark 2010; Nind and Vinha 2013; Nind 2014). During research the public may be involved in data collection (see citizen science), or the methods used themselves may be inclusive (e.g. ethnography, focus groups, living labs). Including the public after the research process may involve working on the results collectively, consulting them with a selected group or stakeholders, or simply communicating and disseminating the findings. The decision whether to employ the participatory methods from the very beginning of the project is up to the project team. The earlier such activities are implemented, the more in-depth the participation is, but it also requires more resources: time and human resources.

Dissemination is an interesting case. It is regarded as a form of cooperation by some (see Warwas et al. 2021, p. 20-21). However, as the dissemination process is unidirectional and typically top-down, I have chosen not to incorporate it into the examples and techniques of science-society cooperation.

Methods of science-society cooperation

There are numerous ways to achieve cooperation between scientists and various societal stakeholders. As noted by Rowe and Fewer

“mechanisms for enacting the participation concept (instruments, techniques, methods, tools, etc.) (...) tend to be loosely defined. These range from simple surveys to complex deliberative approaches involving members of the public taking part in groups or conferences, which attempt to structure the debate and provide balanced information on the issue (e.g., citizens’ juries).” (2005, p. 253).

In this part of the report, I provide a short overview of the available methods and techniques for cooperation between science and society. Due to the small size of the report, I present only a few selected examples.

I outline two distinct groups of methods of cooperation. The first is more extensive and incorporates general approaches such as citizen science and living labs. These approaches are quite recent and innovative and not well defined nor grounded in theory yet. The second group consists of specific methods and techniques that could also be used as part of the broader approaches but are well-defined since they have been used in research for decades. The latter were not designed specifically to fulfil the needs of cooperation within scientific projects. They grew within specific scientific disciplines, like anthropology or sociology, that were sensitive to the inclusion of the research participants from the very beginning.

Table 1 The examples of approaches and techniques/methods used to achieve the cooperation. The table is not exhaustive, it only contains samples selected for the purpose of this report.

Broad approaches	Techniques/methods
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen science • Living labs • Ethnography 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus groups • Participatory mapping • Community dinners

(1) Broad approaches

Citizen science. This is a broad term that refers to the participation of non-expert scientists in data gathering and, to a certain degree, its analysis. As put by Haklay, citizen science involves “scientific activities in which non-professional scientists voluntarily participate in data collection, analysis and dissemination of a scientific project” (Haklay 2013, p 106). Although the concept of involving citizens in science was present even in the 19th century science, the contemporary framework was developed only in the last 30 years (Bonney et al. 2009). Citizen science is often used to gather information such as meteorological, environmental or geographic data, that cannot be obtained otherwise. Examples include projects monitoring the quality of water or air, monitoring the abundance of species like birds, bees or dragonflies but also transcribing the ancient texts or gathering data on web search engines. The citizen science projects supported by EU might be found here: <https://eu-citizen.science/>. However, this approach has also its peculiar shortcomings. Of particular concern are issues of data ownership, conflict of interest and authorship of publications, which is further developed in “Challenges and obstacles of the cooperation” part of the report.

Living Lab(s) – this is a complex approach rather than a specific method. Initially, in the 1990s, it was developed in the context of information technologies, but over time, the living labs have also started to be used for other issues and fields. What they have in common is the goal of integrating the research process into real-world environments. General goal of the Living Lab is to test a solution in the real life where it is going to be later introduced. The European Union in 2006 created a European Network of Living Labs. ”Living labs focus on real-life environments, include stakeholders, and use collaborative methods to innovate and address problems. (...) The living lab methodology focuses on solution generation and experimentation with changes in practice.” (Racine et. al, pp. 154-155). It brings together science, business, government and citizens to test together a proposed solution. There is no one definition of a living lab, they can be defined in various ways and fulfil a range of purposes. They can be described as methodology, ecosystem or even community (Malmberg et al. 2017).

Ethnography. Ethnography is sometimes used as a research technique, but it is also a method and even a branch of science. It is not only a way of creating knowledge but also specific approach to science and data collection. Ethnography is a method specific to anthropology (cultural and social anthropology) and has a long academic tradition. Its roots go back to the end of the 19th century. At the heart of this approach is the equal treatment of research participants and the researcher. The participants' perspective is central to ethnography, as is the need to overcome power relations and inequalities by giving participants voice and agency over their own life stories, beliefs and knowledge. The research takes place in circumstances that are natural to the participants, so it is the researcher who participates (through a method called participant observation) in the lives or activities of the participants and tries to understand them. Knowledge is co-created in the relationship between researcher and participants. Ethnography also places great emphasis on in-depth, long-term fieldwork, which enables the researcher to better understand the phenomena under study. All the further described techniques, such as focus groups, visual methods, workshops or community dinners, might be used as a part of ethnography.

(2) Participatory research techniques.

Focus groups. Bagnoli and Calrk argued, that focus groups can offer participants a space to establish their own categories and labels, while uncovering ideas and opinions through dialogue and debate with others. Focus groups ensure that the knowledge, language, and concepts and classifications used in focus group interactions are coming from the experience of the participants. The participants interact between each other rather than just with the moderator. Therefore, it is not the researcher that generates data, but the participants as a collective (Bagnoli and Clark 2010, pp. 104-105). Therefore this technique ensures that the gathered data is created by the equally treated participants, and the process of the knowledge gathering itself is rather bottom-up.

Workshops. This method creates a safe and creative space for participants to express their worldviews and ideas. It enables the use of various creative techniques such as theatre and drama, storytelling or mapping. The participants actively create the event, they collectively shape its' direction. Workshops, similarly to focus groups, shift the power from the researcher to participants. They are especially useful in discussing issues that are difficult to express verbally due to their creativity and possible engagement of movement.

Visual methods. There is a long tradition of involving members of the community in collaborative data collection by using visual methods such as drawings, pictures, videos, theatre or photography (Hirsch and Philbin 2016). Using visual methods is popular among anthropologists (see e.g. Pink 2021). There are multiple purposes and specific research questions that are answered with the help of visual methods. Hirsch and Philbin list some of the potential uses:

- body mapping;
- community mapping,
- sexuality life lines,
- sunburst diagrams;
- pictorial bar charts;
- time lines and calendars;
- reproductive life lines. (Hirsch and Philbin 2016, p. 265).

Community dinner and discussion. This is very specific type of technique described by Carr and Halvorsen (2001). Among other democratic and participatory techniques (which they call “methods”) they chose community dinners to include the public in the knowledge gathering and decision-making. The method involves the social event where dinner is served, and people can freely talk and discuss chosen issues at the tables. The tables are self-moderated. The technique enables the participants to feel relaxed and assures the topics covered are not imposed by researchers.

Very useful summary of participatory methods may be found in the article “[Participatory Research Methods – Choice Points in the Research Process](#)” by Lisa M. Vaughn and Farrah Jacquez (2020).

It is extremely important to note that the introduction of any kind of participatory method or technique **requires trained and experienced researchers**. All the methods described require appropriate training, knowledge and background. In particular, ethnography is a method with a very long academic tradition and to use it properly and ethically requires a competent ethnographer with a degree in anthropology.

Key success conditions in science-society cooperation

Science-society cooperation requires conditions similar to those for any other scientific or non-scientific project. The most fundamental prerequisite is the presence of two (or more) parties willing to collaborate. The second step is to secure the time and resources needed to proceed with the planned activities (see Nind et al. 2017). It is also important to ensure that a few additional conditions are met.

According to Stawicki and Stępniaak (2023) the key conditions for successful cooperation are not only within the system or the external conditions. Equally important are individual personality traits of the actors cooperating. They list the most frequently mentioned communication and social competencies crucial for cooperation:

- the ability to reduce the complexity of knowledge and communicate it in language devoid of specialized jargon (including the ability to visualize and create coherent narratives);
- the ability to establish and maintain lasting social relationships;
- the ability to recognize partners' often non-verbalized/hard-to-verbalize knowledge needs and translate them into the language of research questions;
- the ability to negotiate, compromise, self-present and demonstrate the practical aspects of scientific knowledge;
- the ability to collaborate in teams consisting of people with diverse competencies and positions.

(Stawicki and Stępniaak 2023, p. 70)

Very useful practical manual for doing inclusive research has been prepared by Melanie Nind and Hilra Vinha from the University of Southampton. They summarized their experiences with doing research with people with special educational needs. They noticed that each new research project comes with its own set of challenges, including overcoming barriers to participation and finding ways to share decision-making power, build essential skills, and navigate complex or uncomfortable spaces in both academia and advocacy (Nind and Vinha 2013, p. 7). Therefore, each participation and cooperation process is unique and must be designed according to the specific circumstances. The authors have identified the most important steps necessary to ensure the successful process of inclusive research. While some of these steps are specific to inclusive research with marginalised groups, which is of particular interest to the authors, others are universal and may be applicable to other forms of cooperation between science and society. In the following section, I highlight some of the key points from their work.

1. **Define everyone's relationship to research.** As the authors have noted, "this could lead to a change in the relationship between those who are the researchers and those who are the researched, so that it becomes more equal, or blurred, or there is more dialogue between the two." (Nind and Vinha 2013, p. 8).
2. **Discussing research objectives and research design together** - making sure that the research topics are in line with the most important issues of the group involved in the research, or making sure that the research is in line with the needs of the group involved.
3. **Ethical issues and trust.** This includes decisions about anonymity, ownership of the research or responsibilities within the mixed group. "The practicalities include ensuring that people moving into positions of partnership in research are neither overburdened nor overprotected. They involve balancing costs and benefits beyond the usual issues of ethical regulation considered by ethics committees." (Nind and Vinha 2013, p. 14)
4. **Selecting appropriate methods and securing funding to do so.** "The added value of working in an inclusive way needs to be tangible, as there is considerable consensus that conducting research in an inclusive way takes more time and is therefore more expensive." (Nind and Vinha 2013, p. 24)
5. **Decide where the emphasis lies.** Is scientific rigour or inclusiveness more important? It is not always possible to fulfil the requirements of both.
6. **Dissemination is not the last step in research.** It happens at all the previous stages.

Figure 2 The most important steps for inclusive research. Own design based on Nind and Vinha 2013.

Challenges and obstacles in cooperation

The field of science-society collaboration is still developing. Since both parties of the collaboration represent different needs and modes of action there are various obstacles and challenges that arise in the process. I discuss a few of them below.

(1) Differences between "science" and "society"

One of the factors that significantly affects the cooperation is the **different rationalities of the actors entering into the process: the science and the society**. Science is a functionally separate system which internal structures and processes are subordinated to the acquisition and codification of information in relation to existing structures of scientific knowledge. Therefore, only information that meets certain criteria can be included in the science systems. For other actors representing the society (like members of the public, public policy makers, etc.), however, the creation and acquisition of knowledge is not an end in itself; rather, knowledge is a tool for achieving various goals (Stawicki and Stępnia 2023, p. 65-66). Also, the "scientific actors" and the "societal actors" have different objectives. While the aim of scientists is usually to create

knowledge, the social stakeholders are often looking for concrete solutions. Moreover, scientists report to funding institutions, while civil servants, for example, must fulfil their official duties. Therefore they are dependent on different evaluation systems which value different outcomes.

For scientists the most tangible benefit from the cooperation is creation of scientific publications. Within the system of science this is what scientists are held accountable for by funding bodies, employers etc. According to the study conducted by Stawicki and Stepniak among scientists, in spite of this, a fairly large percentage of the scientists surveyed carry out projects in cooperation with the society, even though they cannot easily translate it into scientific “achievements”. Despite the lack of scientific output, they also value the financial resources, as well as the social, intellectual and symbolic capital that they can gain from such collaboration (Stawicki and Stępniaak 2023, p. 68).

It should also be mentioned that there is often a significant difference regarding the language used. Whereas the scientific language seeks to precisely describe the complexity of the researched issues, the society is fonder of the straightforward answers and black-and-white descriptions.

Also, as described by Resnik and others, it is extremely important that scientists who work with citizens make very clear from the beginning of the collaboration the rules and division of data ownership and other intellectual property issues with citizen volunteers to ensure mutual understanding (Resnik et al 2015, p. 478). Moreover, regarding the authorship it is extremely important to give citizens appropriate credit for their work, for instance they should be granted authorship if they have made significant contributions to scientific publications (Resnik et al 2015, p. 480).

(2) Financial, human and time resources

Stawicki and Stępniaak (2023) have noted that significant obstacles to effective cooperation can arise from differing operational timeframes across involved actors. This is because social actors (members of the public, policy makers, etc.) often have limited time and seek access to knowledge to address specific, current issues. While scientists typically need more time to fulfill the demands of the scientific process, such as thoroughly engaging with existing literature and following rigorous research methods. While scientists often aim to build and expand knowledge, public policymakers tend to prioritize actionable insights over the accumulation of knowledge itself (Stawicki and Stępniaak 2023, p.73). The time is therefore often a missing resource. The situation is similar for the monetary resources. As mentioned earlier, scientists often report to the funding bodies, that require from them tangible scientific results in the form of, for example, publications. However, the latter cannot be obtained solely through the cooperation with the society. In scientific projects, cooperation is often organized by the same person who is responsible for the research. It may lead to tensions between the

need for delivering scientific outcomes, such as academic peer-reviewed articles, and the outcomes connected to the cooperation. The increasing emphasis on science-society cooperation, its planning, implementation and reporting, while at the same time delivering all the scientific results, puts a lot of pressure on scientists. It takes time, money and people to really build such components into research projects. It is therefore extremely important to budget specifically for this in projects, to employ people especially for this purpose, or to extend the duration of projects, in order to be able to truly collaborate without compromising the quality of the research.

(3) The engagement process

The process of recruiting the participants is difficult and time consuming. Especially if we want to ensure that they represent various groups, including underprivileged, special needs groups and/or minorities. The usual obstacles to the vulnerable groups' participation are following (based on Goedhart et al 2021):

- inclusion criteria that demand a certain level of education or the use of complicated language in invitations to participate;
- lack of acknowledgement that communities consist of multiple groups with different values, norms, and perspectives;
- individual obstacles and barriers to participation, including disabilities, ethnicity, age and economic situation;
- unfamiliarity with research and not perceiving oneself as an expert resulting in limited confidence to share opinions and believe that these views will be heard and acted upon;
- lack of trust in academia perceived as hindering participants from engaging with researchers and from opening up and sharing their stories with researchers;
- low literacy levels or lack of proficiency in the language of the host country – in case of migrant participants;
- costs of participation: costs of transportation or costs of having to give up employment for some time;
- lack of motivation or time, combined with socioeconomic distress, drives people to focus their time and energy on more pressing priorities.

In order to address the issues listed above and thereby ensure the involvement of not only the “usual suspects”, but also citizens from vulnerable groups in the process, it is necessary to involve the following groups in the engagement process: advocacy groups, research funders and researchers. The process should be carefully designed and thought through, which means it is time- and resource-consuming.

(4) A few thoughts from the EmCliC project

With EmCliC, we aimed to address the gap in understanding how climate change affects vulnerable populations and how people experience climate change daily. Our case was urban heat. We focused on the experiences of adults above 65 years old living in two European cities, Warsaw and Madrid. We chose two cities with different climates and the cultural history of adaptation to high temperatures. We implemented interdisciplinary research based on the collaboration between natural and social scientists from social anthropology, sociology, atmospheric physics, climate science and epidemiology. Additionally, we worked in collaboration with a medical doctor and architects. We juxtaposed and combined the large scale, top-down biophysical data and localized and individualized qualitative bottom-up data. We aimed to highlight the embodied knowledge older adults have about urban heat and climate change. Finally, we studied older adults' adaptation strategies to better understand how they experience and adjust to increasing heat in the city.

To some extent we also cooperated with the society, even though the main focus of the project was basic research. We exchanged the ideas and findings with an architectural and artistic initiative Centrala from Warsaw; we co-curated the exhibition at the National Museum in Gdańsk; we organized a Game Jam (an event including artists and programmers) with Ziemniaki Foundation, followed by an art exhibition held at Ochota Cultural Centre in Warsaw. We also established a collaboration with the grassroots ecological organization Ecologists in Action from Madrid who helped us to promote the project results among the citizens of Madrid.

The EmCliC project has demonstrated that when collaborating with external institutions, it is essential to allocate sufficient time and resources. In the event of a mismatch between the project's goals and those of the societal actors, the collaboration risks becoming illusory or failing. Drawing on our experience of working with various societal actors, I highlight the most challenging aspects of the collaboration.

- It is important to note that a research project has a defined lifespan, often a matter of years, whereas public offices, for example those of a municipal nature, are subject to different timetables and are partly dependent on the electoral calendar. In an ideal scenario, cooperation would be established prior to project initiation, ensuring that both parties allocate time and resources for joint activities. In instances where this cooperation is not established prior to project initiation, institutions may face challenges in allocating time and resources for joint activities, as evidenced in our case. Consequently, they may not fully appreciate the benefits of cooperation or the way they can contribute to the project.
- Scientific goals, especially those within research projects that focus on basic research, often do not align with institutional goals. Institutional goals often prioritize solutions and results that can be readily implemented. In such cases, it

is advisable to engage in early planning of the collaboration. This approach ensures that the project's research questions and goals align with the interests of the society. This participatory research planning approach is a key aspect missing from the literature on science-society cooperation.

- In order to successfully collaborate with individuals from outside the academic sector (in our case, art curators and programmers), it is essential to simplify the academic findings. While a significant part of the project involved analysing the complexity of the studied phenomena, urban heat, to formulate a straightforward message suitable for the game design, as stipulated in the game jam event, we were compelled to relinquish a substantial portion of our findings, as they were not applicable.
- A serious obstacle we encountered during the project was the need expressed by the funding body to formalize the cooperation. Whereas this need is understandable from the perspective of project reporting, for the perspective of the real-life cooperation it limited our options to the established institutions, like registered non-governmental organizations, foundations or museums. Through the project we collaborated with local communities and senior citizens, who were the research participants in ethnographic research, focus groups and workshops, though this was in no way formalized therefore did not “count” as science-society cooperation in evaluation.

Evaluation of science-society cooperation

To be able to evaluate any kind of activity it is necessary to have a clear goal before the process starts. That is why it is important to establish the cooperation prior to the start of the project or at its early stages (see previous parts of the report). According to Rowe and Frewer (2005), the effectiveness of science-society cooperation might be evaluated at least in two different aspects. One concerns **the process itself, its fairness, clarity, transparency etc.**, and the second focuses on its **effectiveness**, if the process led to achieving the intended purpose. To be able to thoroughly evaluate the process of science-society cooperation, evaluation should be planned as a final stage of the project.

The goals of science-society collaboration mentioned in the literature are as follows:

- Based on values: democratization of the process, inclusiveness, non-hierarchical research process;
- Improving the scientific value of the research by gathering the data not available otherwise;
- Incorporating the values and beliefs of the studied communities and groups;
- Implementing the research results into the policies, procedures etc.;
- Transferring the knowledge to the society;

- Assuring the knowledge produced by the project is adequate for the public needs. As Andrea Cornwall and Rachel Jewkes put it, the participatory research “focuses on “knowledge for action”, achieved through partnerships between traditionally trained researchers and laypeople in a community” rather than purely on “knowledge for understanding” (Cornwall and Jewkes 1995);
- Deepening the understanding of the research matters and phenomena, as in case of ethnography.

Once the goal of the collaboration is established, it becomes possible to evaluate whether it has been achieved. Here are some examples of questions that can be asked during the evaluation of science-society cooperation:

- Were the participants demographically representative of the communities as a whole?
- Did techniques used in the process contribute to the definition of the public good?
- Did techniques used contribute to the inclusion of the participants’ beliefs and values in the process?

Figure 3 Sample evaluation questions, based on Carr and Halvorsen 2001, pp. 113-114.

Referring to the typology from the beginning of the Report, I demonstrate below how process efficiency has been defined by the Rowe and Fewer (2005).

Public communication	Maximizing the relevant information from the sponsor and efficiently transferring it (with minimal information loss) to the maximum number of the relevant population, with the efficient processing of that information by the receivers (the public/participants).
Public consultation	Maximizing the relevant information from the maximum number of the relevant population and efficiently transferring it (with minimal information loss) to the sponsor, with the efficient processing of that information by the receivers (the sponsors).
Public participation	Maximizing the relevant information from the maximum number of all relevant sources and transferring it (with minimal information loss) to the other parties, with the efficient processing of that

	information by the receivers (the sponsors and participants) and the combining of it into an accurate composite.
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Figure 4 Effectiveness of the three types of approaches, own design, based on Rowe and Fewer 2005, p. 263.

The specific evaluation techniques might be chosen according to the specific project needs, it could be either quantitative (surveys among all the participants) or more qualitative, like interviews. Evaluation is crucial in order to understand what worked and what did not in the process.

The description above focused on the evaluation of the science-society cooperations implemented within the projects. However, there is another kind of evaluation of such initiatives and processes, that is the evaluation of the academic projects by funding bodies. Since the goal of EU valorisation policy is to increase the value of research projects in their social and economic aspects, all academic projects across the EU will be increasingly evaluated based on their science-society cooperation. However, it is very difficult to come up with indicators that would capture the project's cooperation with the society in its specificity. The quantitative indicators, on the one hand, might be easier to gather and assess, however, they might in fact hinder the kinds of cooperation implemented, and do not fully allow to evaluate the quality and depth of the cooperation. Qualitative indicators, on the other hand, though better suited to evaluate the quality of the collaboration process, are more difficult to collect and might in fact add additional administrative burden on the scientists. Moreover, the evaluation emphasis is often placed on the impact of research on economic growth and innovation, and less so on its impact on the society and social actors.

Summary

The key elements for a successful cooperation between science and society are as follows:

- At the outset, when planning the project, it is essential to include a cooperative element in the research project or project proposal. This approach ensures the procurement of essential resources and the implementation of suitable methodologies. Additionally, engaging with the public during the project design stage can facilitate their involvement and interest in the research questions.
- It is also beneficial for the funding body to not limit potential collaborations to specific institutional types. By not limiting cooperation to specific institutions, we can expand the available options.
- The concept of cooperation encompasses more than just the collaboration between two institutions. The stage of the research also requires consideration.

Participative, qualitative research methods enable scientists to genuinely democratise the research process and include marginalised groups.

- Prior to the establishment of any cooperative relationships, it is essential to allocate time and resources to deliberate on the potential partnerships. Despite the emphasis on democratising science and fostering cooperation, there is still a lack of resources and a hierarchical, insular scientific system in the Polish context (Jedlikowska 2020). It is therefore essential to make a concerted effort to include all relevant groups in the project.
- It is also vital to clearly state the goals of the partnership and ensure all parties involved have the same understanding of the goals and means of cooperation.
- Not every research project needs to be based on science-society collaboration.
- **To implement good science-society cooperation within research projects, such projects need more time, funding and human resources to plan, conduct and report on such cooperations.**
- It is important to remember about the difference regarding the language used by scientific actors and societal actors and allocate time in the project for discussing the differences and translating the scientific outcomes to the more common language.
- Each participation and cooperation process is unique and must be designed according to the specific circumstances.
- It is a good practice to plan an evaluation of the cooperation. This will enable the actors of cooperation to learn what worked well and what did not.

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